

SEMI-ANALYTICAL POST-BUCKLING AND ULTIMATE STRENGTH ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE PLATES

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1 Introduction

Fibre reinforced composite plates are used as one of the main structural components, for example in certain types of ships and most wind turbine blades. For analysis of such large structures, nonlinear finite element methods can be applied in a design situation. However, these analyses require special expertise and are normally time consuming in terms of model generation, numerical computation and post-processing. As an alternative, computationally efficient analysis tools using semi-analytical methods for buckling and strength predictions have become common. Previously, for use in estimating the ultimate strength of stiffened and unstiffened, thin steel plates under in-plane compression, several simplified semi-analytical approaches have been developed by Steen [1] and by Brubak *et al.* [2,3,4]. The aim of the present work is to extend these methods to plates made of fibre-reinforced composites having a wide range of thicknesses. The paper presents the strength analysis of simply supported composite plates subjected to uniaxial in-plane compression load using such a semi-analytical method. The method is able to take account of:

- failure and degradation models for composites,
- initial geometric imperfections,
- out-of-plane shear deformations, and
- post-buckling deformations.

Further, two different types of degradation approaches, in combination with the Hashin failure criterion from 1973 [5] have been developed:

- Complete ply degradation model (CPDM).
- Ply region degradation model (PRDM).

To validate the method, the results are compared with the parametric studies conducted by Misirlis using ABAQUS, reported by Hayman *et al.* [6].

2 Displacements and Strains

2.1 Strains

Classical large deflection theory combined with first order shear deformation theory have been used. The nonlinear strains including the initial imperfection are defined by [7,8]:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{xx} &= \varepsilon_{xx}^0 + z\kappa_{xx} \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w_{init}}{\partial x} \right) \\ &\quad + z \left(\frac{\partial \phi_x}{\partial x} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (1a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{yy} &= \varepsilon_{yy}^0 + z\kappa_{yy} \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \frac{\partial w_{init}}{\partial y} \right) \\ &\quad + z \left(\frac{\partial \phi_y}{\partial y} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (1b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{xy} &= \gamma_{xy}^0 + z\kappa_{xy} = \left(\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w_{init}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \frac{\partial w_{init}}{\partial x} \right) \\ &\quad + z \left(\frac{\partial \phi_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \phi_y}{\partial x} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (1c)$$

$$\gamma_{xz} = \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + \phi_x \quad (1d)$$

$$\gamma_{yz} = \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} + \phi_y \quad (1e)$$

The terms with the superscript “0” denote the mid-plane membrane strains, while κ are the curvatures. Further, u_0 and v_0 are the mid-plane displacement fields in the x - and y -directions, respectively. The out-of-plane displacement is given by w , and w_{init} is an initial out-of-plane imperfection. Further, z is the distance from the middle plane of the plate. The rotations of a transverse normal about axes parallel to the y and x axes are given by ϕ_x and ϕ_y , respectively.

2.2 Boundary Conditions and Displacements

Fig. 1. Plate geometry and load condition.

A simply supported plate is considered, with dimensions $a \times b$ (Fig.1) and an initial deformation w_{init} . The plate is simply supported on all edges and subjected to a mean compression N_x in the x -direction. In the analyses, this is achieved by restraining the edge $x = 0$ in the x -direction and applying a uniform, negative displacement u_c in the x -direction on the edge $x = a$, all edges being held straight. The total out-of-plane deformation is $w_{tot} = w_{init} + w$, where w is the additional deformation induced by the load N_x . Each deformation component is assumed in the form of a truncated double Fourier series [4,9]:

$$u_0(x,y) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M u_{mn} \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right) + u_c \frac{x}{a} \quad (2a)$$

$$v_0(x,y) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M v_{mn} \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right) + v_c \frac{y}{b} \quad (2b)$$

$$\phi_x(x,y) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M x_{mn} \cos\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right) \quad (2c)$$

$$\phi_y(x,y) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M y_{mn} \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \cos\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right) \quad (2d)$$

$$w_{tot}(x,y) = w(x,y) + w_{init}(x,y) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M w_{mn} \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right) + \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M w_{imn} \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right) \quad (2e)$$

The coefficients u_c , v_c , u_{mn} , v_{mn} , x_{mn} , y_{mn} and w_{mn} are unknown. Further, m , n , M and N are positive integers, and w_{imn} are given imperfection amplitudes.

3 Potential Energy

The total potential energy consists of three contributions associated, respectively, with in-plane strain energy, transverse shear strain energy and external forces:

$$\Pi = U_p + U_s + U_f \quad (3)$$

The in-plane strain energy can be divided into a membrane contribution and a bending contribution, and then U_p can be written as

$$U_p = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \varepsilon_p^T \sigma_p dV = \frac{1}{2} \int_A \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \varepsilon_p^T \bar{Q} \varepsilon_p dz dA = \frac{1}{2} \int_A \left((\varepsilon^0)^T A \varepsilon^0 + 2(\varepsilon^0)^T B \kappa + \kappa^T D \kappa \right) dA = U_m + U_{mb} + U_b \quad (4)$$

where U_m and U_b are the membrane and bending strain energies, respectively, and U_{mb} is the strain energy due to the coupling terms between the membrane and bending contributions. The extensional stiffness matrix is given by A , while B

and D are the bending-stretching coupling matrix and the bending stiffness matrix, respectively.

The transverse shear strain energy is given in equation (5):

$$U_s = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s^T \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s dV = \frac{1}{2} \int_A \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s^T \bar{\mathbf{Q}}_s \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s dz dA$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} k \int_A \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s^T A_s \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s dA \quad (5)$$

Here, A_s is the stiffness matrix for transverse shear and k ($= 5/6$) is the shear correction coefficient.

The potential energy of an external, in-plane load N_x in the x -direction is given by

$$U_f = \Lambda N_x b u_c \quad (6)$$

where Λ is a load parameter and b is the width of the plate.

4 Solution Procedure

4.1 Incremental Response Propagation

The post-buckling response is traced by an incremental procedure [1]. Here, an arc length parameter is used as a propagation parameter.

Using large deflection theory, the equilibrium equations obtained from the Rayleigh-Ritz method are nonlinear. Instead of solving the nonlinear equations directly, these are solved incrementally by computing the rate form of the equilibrium equations with respect to an arc length parameter η . Further, the change in the arc length parameter is associated with a change in the external load and the displacement/rotation. For an external applied load, changing proportionally with Λ , this relationship is illustrated graphically in Fig. 2.

As the increment size approaches zero, the relationship can be given by

$$\dot{\Lambda}^2 + \sum_{Displ.} \frac{\dot{\lambda}_i^2}{t^2} + \sum_{Rot.} \dot{\lambda}_i^2 = 1 \quad (7)$$

where λ_i represents the displacement and rotation amplitudes and t is the plate thickness. A dot above a

symbol indicates differentiation with respect to the arc length parameter η .

Fig. 2. Relationship between an arc length parameter increment $\Delta\eta$, a load increment $\Delta\Lambda$ and an incremental displacement amplitude $\Delta\lambda_i$.

In the incremental procedure, the load parameter Λ and displacement/rotation amplitudes λ_i are functions of the arc length parameter η . For an increment $\Delta\eta$ along the equilibrium curve from point s to $(s+1)$, a Taylor series expansion gives

$$\lambda_i^{s+1} = \lambda_i^s + \dot{\lambda}_i^s \Delta\eta + \frac{1}{2} \ddot{\lambda}_i^s \Delta\eta^2 + \dots \quad (8a)$$

$$\Lambda^{s+1} = \Lambda^s + \dot{\Lambda}^s \Delta\eta + \frac{1}{2} \ddot{\Lambda}^s \Delta\eta^2 + \dots \quad (8b)$$

The second and higher order terms are neglected in the present work, i.e. the expansion is of first order, since by choosing a sufficiently small increment the results achieved by this first order expansion are satisfactory. Besides, retaining the second or higher order terms is computationally costly and will not likely give significant computational gains [10].

4.2 Incremental Equilibrium Equations

The Rayleigh-Ritz method in an incremental form or rate form as mentioned in Section 4.1 has been used to solve the problem. The total potential energy is given by equation (3). Equilibrium requires that $\delta\dot{\Pi} = 0$, and thus

$$\frac{\partial \dot{\Pi}}{\partial \lambda_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \left(\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial \lambda_i} \right) = C_{ij} \dot{\lambda}_j + F_i \dot{\Lambda} = 0 \quad (9)$$

where

$$C_{ij} = \frac{\partial^2 \Pi}{\partial \lambda_i \partial \lambda_j} \text{ and } F_i = \frac{\partial^2 \Pi}{\partial \lambda_i \partial \Lambda} \quad (10)$$

Here, C_{ij} is a generalised, incremental stiffness matrix and $F_i \dot{\Lambda}$ is a generalised, incremental load vector. Further, i indicates the row number, while j indicates the column number in a matrix. The total number of unknowns is $N_{tot} + 1$ (λ_i and Λ), while there are N_{tot} equations in equation (9). The additional equation required is equation (7).

4.3 Procedure for Solving the Equations

First, $\dot{\lambda}_j$ and $\dot{\Lambda}$ can be found by solving the equations (7) and (9). The solution of equation (9) is given by

$$\dot{\lambda}_j = -\dot{\Lambda} C_{ij}^{-1} F_i \quad (11)$$

Substituting equation (11) into equation (7):

$$\dot{\Lambda}^2 \left(t^2 + \sum_{Displ.} (C_{ij}^{-1} F_i)^2 + t^2 \sum_{Rot.} (C_{ij}^{-1} F_i)^2 \right) = t^2 \quad (12)$$

Then, from equation (12), the load rate parameter $\dot{\Lambda}$ can be determined as

$$\dot{\Lambda} = \pm \frac{t}{\sqrt{t^2 + \sum_{Displ.} (C_{ij}^{-1} F_i)^2 + t^2 \sum_{Rot.} (C_{ij}^{-1} F_i)^2}} \quad (13)$$

According to equation (13), there are two possible solutions with the same numerical values, but opposite signs along the equilibrium curve. For choosing the correct solution, the angle criterion is applied. Based on the assumption that the equilibrium curve is smooth, it is desired to find the solution giving a continuous increase of the arc length. This is achieved by the requirement that the absolute value of the angle between the tangents of the consecutive increments ($s - 1$) and s in the load-displacement/rotation space is smaller than 90° . For the positive sign of the load rate $\dot{\Lambda}^s$ at stage s , the following equivalent criterion must be satisfied [1]:

$$\dot{\Lambda}^s \left(\frac{\sum_{Displ.} (-C_{ij}^{-1} F_i)^s \dot{\lambda}_j^{s-1}}{t^2} + \sum_{Rot.} (-C_{ij}^{-1} F_i)^s \dot{\lambda}_j^{s-1} + \dot{\Lambda}^{s-1} \right) > 0 \quad (14)$$

When $\dot{\Lambda}^s$ at stage s is found, the displacement and rotation rate amplitudes $\dot{\lambda}_j^s$ at the same stage are given by equation (11). The displacement and rotation amplitudes, and load parameter at the next stage are then obtained by the first order Taylor series expansion:

$$\lambda_j^{s+1} = \lambda_j^s + \dot{\lambda}_j^s \Delta \eta \quad (15a)$$

$$\Lambda^{s+1} = \Lambda^s + \dot{\Lambda}^s \Delta \eta \quad (15b)$$

As mentioned in Section 4.1, $\Delta \eta$ has to be small to give a satisfactory result. The solution propagation is continued until a given failure criterion is reached.

5 Progressive Failure Model

5.1 Hashin Failure Criterion

The 1973 Hashin failure criterion for in-plane stresses can be written [5]:

$$f_1^T = \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_t} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (16a)$$

$$f_1^C = \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_c} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (16b)$$

$$f_2^T = \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y_t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (16c)$$

$$f_2^C = \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y_c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (16d)$$

Failure occurs when any of the four failure functions from equations (16) reaches unity. Each is associated with a dominant failure mode.

5.2 Degradation of Properties

When failure occurs in a laminated composite plate,

the effective material properties change. This results in a new stiffness of the plate. To describe this behaviour, a damaged stiffness matrix for in-plane deformations is defined [6]:

$$[R]= \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_1)R_{11} & (1-d_1)(1-d_2)R_{12} & 0 \\ sym. & (1-d_2)R_{22} & 0 \\ sym. & sym. & (1-d_6)R_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

Here d_1 is the damage factor in the longitudinal (fiber) direction of the material, d_2 is the damage factor in the transverse direction, and d_6 is the damage factor in the in-plane shear component. The remaining parameters in equation (21) are defined as

$$R_{11} = \frac{E_1}{\Delta}, \quad R_{22} = \frac{E_2}{\Delta}, \quad R_{12} = \frac{\nu_{12}E_2}{\Delta}, \quad R_{66} = G_{12} \quad \text{and} \\ \Delta = 1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}(1-d_1)(1-d_2).$$

The transverse (out-of-plane) shear stiffness matrix, following Misirlis [6], this is not degraded during the analysis. (The ABAQUS shell elements used by Misirlis do not allow such degradation of the transverse shear properties.)

The instantaneous degradation of material properties is used in the progressive failure model reported here. When any ply or region fulfils a stress criterion, its corresponding properties are instantaneously reduced to a predefined value equal to 1% of the respective initial values [11]. Thus the associated damage factor $d_i = 0.99$. In contrast, the FEA results presented in [6] assumed a linear degradation of the properties [12] by using the built-in progressive failure model in ABAQUS.

6 Degradation Models

6.1 Complete Ply Degradation Model (CPDM)

The model presented in this sub-section is based on using the Rayleigh-Ritz method. The boundary conditions are given in Section 2.2 with the corresponding displacement field assumed in equations (2). The total potential energy is provided in equations (3)-(6). The unknown coefficients are found by following the solution procedure described in Section 4.3. In the ply which has exceeded a given stress criterion, the degradation of the corresponding properties is then applied to the entire

ply. The load is then applied with the reduced stiffness until either a further criterion is exceeded in the same ply or failure occurs in a different ply. Again, the associated material degradation is applied to the entire ply. The process is repeated until the maximum value of load is reached; this is considered to be the ultimate load.

6.2 Ply Region Degradation Model (PRDM)

Fig. 3. Plate geometry with regions.

The model presented in this sub-section is based on Fig. 3. A plate with dimensions $a \times b$ has been divided into 9 regions. The assumed displacement fields are in equations (2), while the total potential energy is again given by equation (3)-(6). The unknown displacement and rotation amplitudes are again found by the solution procedure described in Section 4.3. The progressive failure model with degraded material properties is now implemented by reducing the appropriate terms in the equations (4)-(5) in the specific region of the ply where failure has occurred.

7 Results from the Parametric Study

7.1 Parametric Study

The parametric studies have been performed for a series of square plates, with $a = b = 500$ mm, having various breadth/thickness (b/t) ratios. Three different maximum initial imperfection amplitudes have been examined, respectively 0.1%, 1% and 3% of the width b ($= 500$ mm). The assumed shape of the initial geometric imperfection is a single half sine wave in each direction, so that $w_{imn} = 0$ for all values of m and n other than 1. Two different types of composite layup are considered [6]:

- Case A, a triaxial layup: $[-45 / +45 / 0_4 / +45 / -45 / 0_4 / -45 / +45 / 0_3]_S$

This layup configuration is typical for the main spar of a wind turbine blade.

- Case B, a quasi-isotropic, quadriaxial layup: $[0 / +45 / 90 / -45]_{k,s}$

This layup configuration is more typical for ship hull panels that experience a mixture of lateral pressure and in-plane loading due to hull girder bending.

For the triaxial layups (case A), the required b/t values are achieved by scaling the thickness of each individual ply [6]. For the quadriaxial layups (case B), the thickness is increased by adding groups of plies (increasing X) to give the desired b/t values [6]. The material properties and the plate thicknesses for cases A and B are given in Tables 1-3.

For the ply region degradation model (see Fig. 3), regions 1, 3, 7 and 9 are each 160 mm × 160 mm, regions 2 and 8 are each 180 mm × 160 mm, regions 4 and 6 are 160 mm × 180 mm and region 5 is 180 mm × 180 mm.

Table 1. Material properties.

Property	Value	Units
E_1	49627	MPa
E_2	15430	MPa
ν_{12}	0.272	-
G_{12}	4800	MPa
G_{13}	4800	MPa
G_{23}	4800	MPa
X_t	968	MPa
X_c	915	MPa
Y_t	24	MPa
Y_c	118	MPa
S_{12}	65	MPa

Table 2. Plate thicknesses and ply thicknesses for case A.

b/t	t (mm)	t_0 (mm)	$t_{\pm 45}$ (mm)
10	50.00	1.95	0.59
20	25.00	0.97	0.30
50	10.00	0.39	0.12

Table 3. Plate thicknesses and ply thicknesses for case B.

b/t	t (mm)	X	$t_0, t_{\pm 45}, t_{90}$ (mm)
62.50	8.00	1	1.00
20.83	24.00	3	1.00
10.42	48.00	6	1.00

7.2 Step Size

As mentioned in Section 4.1, computational accuracy is dependent on the chosen propagation parameter value $\Delta\eta$. In most of the cases investigated, $\Delta\eta = 0.10$ gives reasonably accurate results within acceptable computational time. For thin plates and plates with few plies, smaller step size needs to be considered. For case B, $t = 8$ mm, $\Delta\eta = 0.01$ has been implemented.

7.3 Ultimate Strength Predictions Using CPDM

The total number of degrees of freedom is defined by the total number of terms given in equations (2). For case A with plate thickness $t = 10.02$ mm, it has been implemented with $N = M = 9$, giving a total of 407 degrees of freedom. For $t = 24.94$ mm and $t = 49.98$ mm in case A, it has been implemented with 127 degrees of freedom ($N = M = 5$). For case B, $t = 8$ mm, 407 degrees of freedom have been applied, while it was found necessary to include 247 degrees of freedom ($N = M = 7$) for $t = 24$ mm and $t = 48$ mm with 3% imperfection. The remaining cases are considered with 127 degrees of freedom.

The results using CPDM are given in Tables 4-5 for cases A and B, respectively. For a given initial geometric imperfection and plate thickness t , the first ply failure stress (σ_{FPF}) and the ultimate strength (σ_{max}) are shown, and the ultimate strength predictions are compared to the FE analyses performed by Misirlis (σ_{max} from [6]). The ratio of these results is provided in the last column of the tables and is again shown in Figs 4-5 for various values of plate thickness t and imperfection amplitude.

Table 4. Results for case A using CPDM.

Imp. % of b	t (mm)	σ_{FPF} (MPa)	σ_{max} (MPa)	σ_{max} [6]	$\frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_{max} [6]}$
0.1	10.02	39.86	94.94	130	0.73
0.1	24.94	172.00	186.66	240	0.78
0.1	49.98	382.13	453.24	570	0.80
1.0	10.02	31.64	90.92	130	0.70
1.0	24.94	71.64	171.40	235	0.73
1.0	49.98	149.55	374.88	435	0.86
3.0	10.02	22.96	87.73	130	0.67
3.0	24.94	39.05	149.98	218	0.69
3.0	49.98	64.26	292.84	360	0.81

Fig. 4. Case A (triaxial layup) with complete ply degradation model: the ultimate strengths from the analyses are compared to those of Misirlis [6] for a range of plate thickness t and imperfection amplitude.

For the triaxial layup, case A, the outermost 0° plies on the convex side of the plate undergo matrix failure first for all cases except for the thickest plate $t = 49.98$ mm with 0.1% imperfection. For that case, the matrix failure occurs in the outermost -45° ply on the concave side of the plate. Further, the 0° plies often fail first in the centre of the plate, while the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies fail at the corners. The total number of plies is 34 for case A, and all 34 plies have to experience matrix failure before the ultimate strength is reached at the first incidence of fibre failure. This trend is detected for all cases, regardless of thickness or imperfection. From Table 4, the ultimate strength predictions using CPDM are in the range of 14% - 33% smaller than Misirlis's FE analysis. The greatest deviations are observed for the thin plates ($t = 10.02$ mm).

Table 5. Results for case B using CPDM.

Imp. % of b	t (mm)	σ_{FPF} (MPa)	σ_{max} (MPa)	σ_{max} [6]	$\frac{\sigma_{\text{max}}}{\sigma_{\text{max}} [6]}$
0.1	8	29.08	89.95	105	0.86
0.1	24	170.92	177.66	215	0.83
0.1	48	204.13	301.97	340	0.89
1.0	8	27.38	91.51	107	0.86
1.0	24	69.49	171.48	210	0.82
1.0	48	144.77	250.92	302	0.83
3.0	8	26.08	94.11	115	0.82
3.0	24	35.62	162.77	205	0.79
3.0	48	61.70	211.24	260	0.81

Fig. 5. Case B (quadriaxial layup) with complete ply degradation model: the ultimate strengths from the analyses are compared to those of Misirlis [6] for a range of plate thickness t and imperfection amplitude.

For the quadriaxial layup, case B, first ply failure always occurred as matrix failure in the outermost 0° plies on the convex side of the plate for all cases except for the thickest plate $t = 48$ mm with 0.1% imperfection. For that case, the matrix failure occurred in the outermost 90° ply on the concave side of the plate. In general, the 0° and 90° plies often fail first in the centre of the plate, while the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies fail at the corners. For this more balanced layup configuration, according to Table 5, the ultimate strength predictions using CPDM produced a more stable deviation in the range of 11% - 21% compared to Misirlis's ABAQUS results, than for case A layups. For all cases except the thickest plate ($t = 48$ mm) with 0.1% and 1% imperfections, all plies have to experience matrix failure and the ultimate strength is reached at the first, or sometimes the second, occurrence of fibre failure. For the thickest plate with 0.1% imperfection, all $\pm 45^\circ$ plies experienced matrix failure before the occurrence of the ultimate strength, which is at the first incidence of fibre failure in a 0° ply without matrix failure. The similar trend is observed for the thickest plate with 1% imperfection. But this time all $\pm 45^\circ$ plies as well as some of the 0° plies have to experience matrix failure before the occurrence of the ultimate strength, which is again at the first fibre failure in a 0° ply without matrix failure.

7.4 Ultimate Strength Predictions Using PRDM

Again, the total number of degrees of freedom is defined by the total number of terms given in

equations (2). Compared with CPDM, some of the cases need more degrees of freedom due to the division of the plate into regions. Case A, $t = 10.02$ mm, is implemented with 407 degrees of freedom, while $t = 24.94$ mm with imperfections 1% and 3% are implemented with 247 degrees of freedom. The remaining cases need only 127 degrees of freedom. For case B, $t = 8$ mm, 407 degrees of freedom have been included. For the remaining cases, it is necessary to have 247 degrees of freedom.

The results using PRDM are provided in Tables 6-7 for cases A and B, respectively. The ratio of the ultimate strength from the present model to that found by Misirlis is presented in Figs 6 and 7 for different plate thickness t and imperfection amplitude.

Table 6. Results for case A using PRDM.

Imp. % of b	t (mm)	σ_{FPF} (MPa)	σ_{max} (MPa)	σ_{max} [6]	$\frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_{max} [6]}$
0.1	10.02	39.86	106.24	130	0.82
0.1	24.94	172.00	186.68	240	0.78
0.1	49.98	382.13	453.24	570	0.80
1.0	10.02	31.64	99.57	130	0.77
1.0	24.94	71.39	175.34	235	0.75
1.0	49.98	149.55	375.89	435	0.86
3.0	10.02	22.96	96.03	130	0.74
3.0	24.94	38.92	155.30	218	0.71
3.0	49.98	64.26	299.73	360	0.83

Fig. 6. Case A (triaxial layup) with ply region degradation model: the ultimate strengths from the analyses are compared to those of Misirlis [6] for a range of plate thickness t and imperfection amplitude.

For both layup cases, considering first ply failure, there is no detectable difference between CPDM and PRDM. The matrix failures occurred in the same

locations at the same calculated stresses.

For case A, the ultimate strength predictions using PRDM are in the range 14% - 29% smaller than Misirlis's FE analysis. Again, the deviations are smallest for the thickest plate. Further, no clear trend is observed except that at least 90% of the regions have to experience matrix failure before the ultimate strength is attained at the first fibre failure. For the thickest plate with 1% imperfection, the ultimate strength is reached at the first incidence of fibre failure in a region without matrix failure.

Table 7. Results for case B using PRDM.

Imp. % of b	t (mm)	σ_{FPF} (MPa)	σ_{max} (MPa)	σ_{max} [6]	$\frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_{max} [6]}$
0.1	8	29.08	101.71	105	0.97
0.1	24	170.92	178.32	215	0.83
0.1	48	204.13	301.97	340	0.89
1.0	8	27.38	101.54	107	0.95
1.0	24	69.49	177.05	210	0.84
1.0	48	144.77	250.92	302	0.83
3.0	8	26.08	101.86	115	0.89
3.0	24	35.62	170.62	205	0.83
3.0	48	61.70	209.70	260	0.81

Fig. 7. Case B (quadriaxial layup) with ply region degradation model: the ultimate strengths from the analyses are compared to those of Misirlis [6] for a range of plate thickness t and imperfection amplitude.

For case B, the ultimate strength predictions using PRDM, the deviations are in the range of 3% - 19% compared to the ABAQUS results provided by Misirlis. The best results are achieved for a thin plate ($t = 8$ mm). Further, 75% of the regions and 95% of the regions have to suffer matrix failure before the ultimate strength is attained at fibre failure for the thin plate and moderately thick plate (t

= 24 mm), respectively. For the thickest plate, the trend is almost similar to that with CPDM, 75% - 90% of regions have to experience matrix failure before the first incidence of fibre failure in a region without matrix failure gives the ultimate strength.

8 Conclusions

Ultimate strength prediction using a semi-analytical method has been established for simply supported composite plates. The present model is able to take account of post-buckling behaviour, out-of-plane shear deformation and geometric imperfections. Investigations are performed for square plates subjected to in-plane compressive load. Two different types of composite layup are considered. The results have been compared with the FE analysis conducted by Misirlis.

In the first degradation approach, CPDM, fulfilment of the failure criterion at any position in a ply leads to instantaneous degradation of corresponding stiffness properties throughout that ply. The predicted ultimate stresses are 14% - 33% smaller than those of Misirlis for the triaxial layup configuration, case A. The most significant differences are observed for thin plates ($t = 10.02$ mm), these being in the range of 27% - 33%. However, for the quadriaxial layup, case B, the ultimate strength predictions using CPDM produced a more stable deviation in the range of 11% - 21%.

In the slightly more detailed approach, PRDM, the plate is divided into nine regions and the stiffness degradation is limited to the affected regions of a failed ply. Compared to Misirlis's ABAQUS results, the deviations are in the range of 14% - 29% for the ultimate strengths predicted for case A, while for the balanced layup configuration, case B, the differences are in the range of 3% - 19%.

The analyses with PRDM thus provide better estimates for many of the cases. Especially for thin plates, characterised by small ply thicknesses (case A) and few plies (case B), PRDM gives appreciably better results. Region based material degradation results in smaller stiffness-reduced areas compared to ply based material degradation. The total plate stiffness will increase significantly for these plates, even with a small number of regions undamaged. The greatest improvements, 7% - 11%, between the predictions using CPDM and PRDM are observed

for the quadriaxial layup configuration, case B. For case A, the improvements are about 7% - 9%. The improvements obtained (0% - 4%) are either negligible or quite small for moderately thick and thick plates for both layup cases. This could be explained by the fact that many plies and regions have to fail before the ultimate strength is reached. The few regions left with intact material properties are unlikely to affect the total plate stiffness significantly, since thicker plates have more plies and greater ply thicknesses.

Predictions using both CPDM and PRDM are still somewhat conservative when compared to Misirlis's analyses. This could be explained by the fact that a linear degradation of the material properties has been assumed in the ABAQUS progressive failure model, while the current analyses assume instantaneous degradation of the material properties. To improve the agreement and give a more accurate estimation of the ultimate stresses, future extension of the work will implement a linear degradation model combined with PRDM. However, it should be noted that Misirlis observed that in some cases the linear degradation model overestimated the ultimate strength [13], so validation against other sources is also needed. Further, the layup configurations investigated in Section 7 are two extreme cases. In order to have a better overall picture of the trends, other layups should be considered. For instance it could be interesting to analyse a more balanced triaxial layup and a more unbalanced quadriaxial layup.

A reliable method for quick strength estimations is always appreciated in design situation and in other studies requiring a larger numbers of cases analysed. FE analyses are often time consuming in these situations and do have their own limitations (as mentioned in Section 5.2). The present method represents a good alternative due to its user friendliness and efficiency. It is often possible to have tailor-made approaches for specific cases with certain load and boundary conditions. However, the method is still in a development phase, and the computational time required is in the range of 30 minutes to several hours on a computer with 3.2 GHz processor and 4 GB RAM. Therefore, optimising the computer code is a part of the planned future work.

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